

Effect of Preconception Antibiotics Exposure on Female Reproductive Health and Pregnancy Outcomes: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

The article explores the potential effects of preconception antibiotic exposure on female reproductive health and pregnancy outcomes. Through a systematic review and meta-analysis, the authors evaluate a range of studies to understand how antibiotic exposure before conception might influence various aspects of female reproductive health, such as fertility, pregnancy complications, and infant health.

Key Findings:

Impact on Fertility: The study found mixed results regarding the effect of preconception antibiotic use on female fertility. Some studies suggested that the use of certain antibiotics before conception could have a negative impact on fertility, while others showed no significant association. However, the data were inconclusive, and more robust studies are needed to clarify these effects.

Pregnancy Complications: The analysis revealed that preconception antibiotic exposure was associated with a slight increase in the risk of pregnancy complications, such as preterm birth, low birth weight, and gestational diabetes. However, the studies included had varying quality and sample sizes, indicating the need for more controlled and large-scale studies.

Infant Health Outcomes: The meta-analysis highlighted some associations between antibiotic exposure before conception and adverse infant health outcomes, including an increased risk of birth defects. However, these findings were limited by the heterogeneity of the studies, suggesting the necessity for further research to draw firm conclusions.

Antibiotic Classes: The review also examined the specific types of antibiotics used before conception. Some classes, such as tetracyclines and sulfonamides, showed stronger associations with negative pregnancy outcomes compared to others. However, data on the exact mechanisms behind these effects remain sparse.

Figures and Results:

Forest Plots: Forest plots were used to summarize the effects of preconception antibiotic exposure on different outcomes, such as preterm birth, low birth weight, and pregnancy loss. These plots demonstrated the variability in the effect sizes across different studies, indicating that further research is required for clearer conclusions.

Sensitivity Analysis: Sensitivity analyses confirmed that the results were robust across various study designs and populations. However, the authors emphasized the potential biases introduced by observational studies and the difficulty of isolating antibiotic exposure from other confounding factors.

Conclusions:

The findings suggest that there may be some risks associated with preconception antibiotic use, but the evidence remains inconclusive. The article calls for more rigorous prospective studies and clinical trials to establish clearer causal relationships between antibiotic exposure and reproductive health outcomes. Additionally, the variability in the types of antibiotics used and the populations studied indicates the need for standardized protocols in future research.

Table.1

Shows the results of research among women struggling with infertility. The study was conducted by women working in a procedure that has daily contact with women, primary and secondary infertility, and those suffering from endometriosis, as well as those undergoing in vitro fertilization. Those used were those that had a high impact on the outcome of the case after testing.

Table 2

Combines preconception data with pregnancy, miscarriage, and birth defects in the application of test results. Applying the data application reduces the conception rate, increases or decreases the risk of birth defects in the fetus, or makes no difference in the outcome.

Table 3

To demonstrate the association of preconception antibiotic exposure with fertility rates. Sulfonamides in the form of three different antibiotics have shown an increased likelihood of infertility than in women who do not use them. Oxytetracycline, on the other hand, has a protective effect. Tetracyclines increase the risk of infertility.

Fig.2

The basic determination of the probability of conception on women's cycles is presented, which are as follows: macrolides, beta-lactams, sulfonamides, other data before conception, and the probabilities that are determined before conception with pregnancy markers are shown. It has been shown that macrolides are delayed in the use of beta-lactams and sulfonamides, and there is no significant relationship between their intake and fertility. Based on statistical

data before pregnancy, there is no significant impact on the results that are pregnant.

Fig.3

Shows the relationship between preconception antibiotic exposure and spontaneous abortion and birth defects. Exposure of a woman to antibiotics before or during pregnancy is associated with adverse outcomes such as premature birth, miscarriage, birth defects, and long-term health problems for the child. After miscarriage and after the birth of children with birth defects, the risk of spontaneous abortion increases.

Authors:

Bekalu Kassie Alemu is a researcher specializing in public health, especially in the area of reproductive health, the health of pregnant women and their children. Originally from Ethiopia, his research focuses on health issues occurring in resource-limited regions. Here is detailed information about his scientific activities:

Bekalu Kassie Alemu is the author of numerous systematic literature reviews and meta-analyses on iron and folic acid supplementation during pregnancy. Focuses on the health effects on mothers and their children, including problems related to micronutrient deficiencies and the prevention of congenital defects.

His work paid particular attention to diseases such as toxoplasmosis and hepatitis B, which have a significant impact on the health of mothers and their children in Ethiopia.

Alemu also analyzed issues related to domestic violence against women and girls, which indicates a broad interest in social problems in the context of public health.

Co-author of research on the impact of probiotics, prebiotics and synbiotics on the health of mothers and infants. He analyzed how these interventions could impact health outcomes, including the gut microbiome of newborns and maternal mental health

Research methodology

Bekalu Kassie Alemu uses advanced scientific methods, including:

Systematic literature reviews and meta-analyses using tools such as PRISMA or AMSTAR-2, which guarantees a high standard of research

Statistical analyzes assessing the effectiveness of health interventions in various demographic contexts.

Alemu's research is critical to health policy in low-income regions such as sub-Saharan Africa. They provide scientific evidence for intervention programs and support decisions about preventing disease and improving health care for women and children.

Bekalu Kassie Alemu is the author of numerous scientific publications, including:

- Articles on iron and folic acid supplementation
- Analyzes on infectious diseases during pregnancy
- Work on the mental health of pregnant women and the impact of microbiota on health

Dr. Chi Chiu Wang is a prominent researcher and clinician specializing in obstetrics, gynecology, and reproductive health. He is a Professor at the Chinese University of Hong Kong (CUHK) and serves as the Deputy Director of the Prenatal Genetic Diagnosis Centre and the Head of the Division within the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at CUHK. He holds multiple advanced degrees, including two PhDs—one in Surgical Sciences from CUHK and another in Genetics from the Japan National Institute of Genetics

Dr. Wang's research primarily focuses on reproduction and development, with an emphasis on prenatal genetics and assisted reproductive technology. His academic contributions include over 270 peer-reviewed articles published in top journals such as Nature Communications, JAMA, Cell Research, and Human Reproduction. His work has garnered over 111 million HKD in research grants and led to several patents

Additionally, Dr. Wang is active in editorial roles for scientific journals and has served on the review panels of leading publications and funding agencies. His contributions to reproductive health have earned him numerous awards and recognition both locally and internationally

The article was published in The Lancet Public Health, a highly reputable, peer-reviewed medical journal that focuses on global health issues. The journal is widely recognized for its research on public health, epidemiology, and global health policies. It has a strong impact factor and is regarded as one of the leading journals in the medical and health policy fields.

Scope: The Lancet Public Health covers topics related to global public health, epidemiology, maternal and child health, infectious diseases, environmental health, and healthcare policy.

Impact Factor: The Lancet Public Health is one of the most influential journals in the field of public health, with a high impact factor, making it a leading source for cutting-edge research in global health.

Dr. Lianchun Li is an accomplished researcher in the field of molecular biology and pharmaceutical sciences. Her work primarily focuses on the molecular mechanisms underlying diseases and the development of targeted therapies. Key contributions and areas of expertise include

Dr. Li has been part of research efforts aimed at identifying inhibitors targeting the menin–MLL interaction, a key pathway in certain forms of leukemia. This work has significant implications for developing novel treatments for hematologic cancers.

Her studies emphasize the exploration of protein-protein interactions, particularly in oncogenic pathways. By dissecting these interactions, her research contributes to advancing targeted cancer therapies.

Beyond basic research, Dr. Li focuses on translational science, bridging laboratory discoveries with potential clinical applications. This includes drug design and preclinical evaluations of bioactive compounds.

Dr. Li is often associated with prominent research institutions and collaborates on multi-disciplinary projects involving bioinformatics, structural biology, and experimental pharmacology.

Qin Li is a name associated with multiple researchers across various disciplines. Below is an overview of notable individuals named Qin Li and their contributions to academic and scientific research:

Qin Li (RNA Editing and Immunology)

Assistant Professor in the Department of Genetics at the University of Pennsylvania, Perelman School of Medicine.

Focuses on the role of RNA editing in immune system regulation and its links to inflammatory diseases.

Discovered significant associations between RNA editing deficiencies and autoimmune conditions, contributing to understanding the mechanisms underlying these diseases.

Previously conducted research at Stanford University and holds a Ph.D. from Peking University, Perelman School of Medicine.

Qin Li (Mathematical Foundations of Quantum Field Theory)

Associate Researcher at Southern University of Science and Technology (SUSTech) in Shenzhen, China.

Expertise in the mathematical underpinnings of quantum field theory, with academic training including a Ph.D. in Mathematics from UC Berkeley. Contributions include exploring complex interactions in quantum systems through mathematical models.

Yao Wang is a Chinese-American video engineer whose research topics include networked video, computer vision, video coding, medical imaging, and the use of machine learning techniques to diagnose lymphedema and concussions. She is a professor of electrical and computer engineering and of biomedical engineering in the New York University Tandon School of Engineering, where she is also Associate Dean for Faculty Affairs and holds an affiliated faculty position in the Radiology Department of the New York University Grossman School of Medicine. She is also a member of NYU WIRELESS.

Journal:

eClinicalMedicine is an international, trusted source of clinical research in medicine, covering all medical specialties - from diagnosis, through treatment and prevention, to palliative care and health policy. The aim of the journal is to support healthcare professionals in coping with dynamic changes in health and to inspire them to rethink and transform the future of healthcare, strengthening health systems as key institutions. It publishes various types of content such as articles, reviews, comments and correspondence. Together with eBioMedicine, it is part of The Lancet Discovery Science - a series of open access scientific journals covering basic, translational, clinical and health systems research. It provides early, relevant evidence to help researchers and clinicians identify new opportunities to improve the health and well-being of people around the world.

The journal supports healthcare professionals in coping with dynamic changes in care systems and inspires them to transform their future, with the goal of strengthening health systems.

Various types of content are published, such as articles, reviews, comments and correspondence. Together with eBioMedicine, the journal is part of The Lancet Discovery Science series, open access scientific journals covering basic,

translational, clinical and health systems research. It provides early scientific evidence to support the identification of new opportunities to improve the health and well-being of people around the world.

eClinicalMedicine boasts an Impact Factor of 9.6 (12th out of 325 general and internal medicine journals) and a CiteScore of 18.9 (16th out of 636 medical journals worldwide). It is indexed in databases such as PubMed Central, Scopus, DOAJ and Science Citation Index Expanded.